

Controller Integrated Digital Twin – A Boost for Dynamics and Accuracy in Machine Tools and Robots

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Abstract

Digital Twins have gained prominence in various applications, including virtual commissioning and process optimization. However, their use in real-time control systems is relatively new. In this article, we explore an innovative approach where the Digital Twin describes dynamic features of both machine tools and robots, as already implemented in Sinumerik ONE. Two distinct approaches are presented. First, we delve into the SINUMERIK function called Engineered Motion Control (EMC) that uses the Digital Twin to improve the dynamic and productivity of a machine. Next, we address robot modeling. Unlike machines, robot dynamics significantly depend on the pose and requires a more complex model than maps those variations.

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1 Introduction

Well known use cases of Digital Twins cover aspects like virtual commissioning before the physical machine does exist or optimizing the cutting process for production. Using a Digital Twin in real time control systems is rather new. This article provides a first insight into an approach where the Digital Twin describes dynamic features of a machine tool or robot as it is already implemented in Sinumerik ONE. The usage of dynamic models inside NC control systems implies an efficient approach for model generation as well as a good fit to the reality. Two approaches will be presented in this paper.

2 Optimized Dynamic and Productivity

In a first step the SINUMERIK function Engineered Motion Control (EMC) will be outlined.

2.1 Functionality of EMC

The approach is based on a Digital Twin describing a controlled dynamic machine model (Figure 1). The model is used to calculate feedforward control signals that compensate oscillations and cross talk effects affecting the workpiece quality at the tool center point.

The model used for the control is time invariant and consists in a transfer function system mapping the natural frequencies identified from the real machine. A semi-automatic modeling is possible based on frequency responses and the commissioning module Auto Servo Tuning from Sinumerik One. For easiness of implementation, the model is implemented directly as a discrete model [1]. A state control is applied [2]. The strategy for the pole placement aims at maximizing the bandwidth of the system without exiting eigenmodes.

2.2 Benefits of EMC

The control algorithm for the dynamic machine model makes use of the model knowledge and allows to generate optimized outputs. With EMC, the jerk and acceleration can be increased without exiting natural frequencies or increasing quasi-static deformation of the structure. A productivity gain of more than 10 % is usually reached e.g. for finishing operations of milling machines. Moreover, the bandwidth is increase and the contour deviation is reduced by more than 50% for typical milling operations.

Figure 1: Engineered Motion Control. The feedforward control signals of the motor torques (T_{ffw}) and encoder values (y_{model}) are calculated from the controlled Digital Twin.

3 Time Variant Model Extension for Robot

A model-based approach for robots needs to consider that the dynamics strongly depends on the pose. Eigenfrequencies, load inertias for each feed drive and compliance at the tool center point vary significantly over the working space. The Digital Twin within Sinumerik Run MyCC ROCO maps the nonlinear behavior of the robot.

3.1 Modelling approach

The modeling approach is illustrated in figure 2. The model is described physically and consists of lumped masses connected with spring / damper elements. The drive trains are abstracted. This simple description enables the control to evaluate the model in real time [3].

Figure 2: Sketch of a robot model as it is evaluated with Sinumerik Run MYCC ROCO for the whole working area.

3.2 Benefits of this approach

This model-based approach allows to increase the static accuracy of a robot in the workspace up to the range of the repeat accuracy. It also harmonizes significantly the performances of the robot and reduces the dependency between quality of the product and location within the workspace.

As shown on Figure 3, the path accuracy of a robot can be more than doubled with the compensation of cross talk and intalk effects.

Overall, using such a Digital Twin inside the NCK of Sinumerik brings robots much closer to the accuracy of machine tools what is a precondition to use the robot's flexibility also for demanding machining operations.

Figure 3: Path at TCP (measured with laser tracker) during a dynamic displacement. The black trajectory is without ROCO, whereas the red trajectory is with crosstalk and intalk-compensation.

4 References

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